

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

[Building envelope: new concepts, KPI and data (DEM)]

SPOKE 4 – Digital innovation toward sustainable mountain

DELIVERABLE DN.19

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	28/04/2025		V. Serra, S. Fantucci, K. Friji, A.Karanafti
0.5			
0.9			
1			

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the concept, relevant KPIs and results related to the development of a timber based Solar Air Heating Facade (SAHF). The active façade has been designed and optimized with the main aim to enhance energy efficiency of building envelopes, by reducing heat loss, exploiting solar gain and integrating ventilation, so to be used both in existing and new buildings. Moving from a conventional solution (i.e a Trombe Wall), polycarbonate panels, reflective coatings and Silica-Aerogel infill have been adopted in order to improve its energy performance, as well as a lamella covering system has been specifically designed to increase its architectural integration. A combined experimental and numerical approach was used to assess the influence of material properties, lamellas geometry, and configuration on the system's thermal resistance, solar transmission and ventilation efficiency. The analyses compared different façade modes such as Thermal Buffer (TB), Indoor Air Curtain (IAC), and Supply Air Facade (SAF) under different environmental and operational conditions. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were also validated against experimental data to support design decisions and performance evaluation. The findings aims to contribute to the development and market penetration of adaptive, high-performance façade systems for energy-efficient building applications.

Introduction

In the European Union, buildings are responsible for 40% of final energy demand and approximately 36% of greenhouse gas emissions [1]. A significant share of this energy consumption is attributed to the poor thermal performance of envelope components. Currently, it is estimated that roughly 75% of the existing EU building stock is energy inefficient [2]. The building envelope plays a major role in regulating heat flows, solar gains, and air renewal, directly impacting both the energy performance and the indoor comfort of buildings. As a result, retrofitting existing buildings with advanced envelope solutions has become a key strategy for meeting energy efficiency targets and enhancing climate resilience. However, this process faces specific challenges, including extreme seasonal temperature variations, significant heat losses through facades, and the need to balance technical performance with the preservation of local architectural aesthetics. In response to these challenges, recent research has proposed innovative envelopes that go beyond conventional insulation. Among these, the integration of ventilation into passive façade systems has been explored as a strategy to reduce energy consumption [3]. This includes retrofitting traditional cavity walls into ventilated cavity walls to enhance cooling efficiency, as well as modifying double-skin façade designs [4]. The integration of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) into the building envelope has emerged as a promising approach. PCMs can store and release latent heat during their phase transition processes, which contributes to improving the thermal inertia of the building [5]. Transparent Insulation Materials (TIMs) are an innovative category of thermal insulation solutions designed to minimize heat losses by incorporating air gaps or evacuated spaces which operates similarly to conventional insulation by limiting heat transfer through strategically placed air voids. Despite their insulating properties, TIMs allow solar radiation to pass through, making them particularly well-suited for enhancing solar gains in outdoor thermal systems [6]. Their performance is generally assessed based on two main

indicators: solar transmittance and heat loss coefficient. The working principle behind TIMs relies on the difference in wavelength between incoming solar radiation, which is absorbed, and the infrared radiation emitted by the absorber. Within this context innovative materials such as silica aerogel are regarded as very interesting for use in highly energy efficient envelopes. Aerogels offer remarkable optical characteristics, including high levels of light and solar transmittance, along with superior thermal insulation when compared to conventional glass. These properties make them suitable for use as transparent wall elements in solar collectors [7]. The proper integration of these solutions not only limit thermal transmittance but also allow the façade to dynamically adapt to external climatic conditions, providing both passive and active control of heat gains and losses. In particular, Solar Air Heating Facades (SAHF) and Trombe wall systems have shown potential for improving the thermal performance of buildings by capturing and distributing solar energy while providing adequate thermal insulation. Assessing the performance of these systems needs a combined use of key performance indicators (KPIs) that capture both their thermal behaviour and their interaction with solar radiation. The performance can be evaluated by means of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) such as the thermal transmittance (U-value), solar transmittance (τ) and solar reduction factor (RF). The experiment focuses on a lamella-integrated Trombe SAHF wall prototype, which was investigated in a double-chamber climatic unit (BET-CELL) and on a real building. Specifically, the experimental set-up enabled the precise measurement of the solar transmission behaviour of polycarbonate-based components, with and without the integration of Silica-Aerogel and lamella systems with various surface coatings (wood, white coating, aluminium). Subsequent to this, real-scale monitoring was conducted to compare the behaviour of this façade with and without lamella and to analyse the performance under real weather conditions and building operational loads. The analysis on the full-scale prototype covered two distinct phases: the first, conducted during the winter 2023–2024, collecting continuous data on the system without the integration of lamella; the second, winter 2024–2025, which was aimed at evaluating the impact of the lamellas and new configurations on the performance. The choice of configurations to be tested was supported by extensive preliminary experimental testing of prototype models under controlled conditions in the BET-CELL climatic chamber. To support the experimental findings, a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model was developed and validated under steady-state conditions for the configuration without lamella. This simulation aimed to replicate the thermal behavior observed in the experimental setup, providing a robust tool for predicting performance and guiding design decisions.

A) Novel concept for Solar Air Heating Façades

This section briefly explains the concept behind a Solar Air Heating Façade, the main layers and its operation modes

A Solar Air Heating Façade (SAHF) can be generally constituted by three main functional layers:

1. An external transparent/translucent layer, to guarantee the transmission of the solar irradiance
2. A massive wall, to guarantee the solar absorption and the heat storage behind the transparent layer
3. An air cavity which separates the external transparent layer from the massive wall. This functional layer allows the circulation of the passive heated air that is generally introduced to the indoor environment.

It can be classified according to the air flow path (origin/destination) in three main categories that can be also considered different operational modes:

- Supply Air Façade (SAF): when the air flow is determined by the introduction of solar pre-heated fresh air coming from the outdoor environment. This façade typology provides a reduction of heat losses, passive heating, and natural ventilation.
- Indoor Air Curtain (AIC): when the air origin is inside as well as the destination. In this closed loop the air passing through the façade is only pre-heated. This façade typology provides a reduction of heat losses, and passive heating.
- Thermal Buffer (TB): there is no circulation of air in the cavity. This façade generally provides a reduction of heat losses.

The concept developed was aimed at enhancing both the architectural integration and thermal performance of the SAHF system. The integration of forced ventilation was specifically chosen to enhance thermal regulation and control of the indoor environment temperature. This active approach, unlike conventional passive SAHF systems, enables the adjustment of airflow rates in response to varying thermal loads and environmental conditions.

Concerning the functional layers two complementary strategies have been proposed: the first involves improving the insulating performance of the transparent element by filling the air cavity of the transparent layer with a translucent material, such as silica-Aerogel, which offers low thermal conductivity while maintaining high solar transmittance. The second strategy focuses on the application of horizontal wooden lamella with optimized solar reflectance, which not only enhances visual appeal but also contributes to the system's energy performance by managing solar gains.

B) KPI and metrics

This section introduces KPI and metrics able to describe the performance of this dynamic envelope. Equations related to solar efficiency, effective efficiency, and thermal buffering efficiency are introduced to evaluate the behavior of the tested Trombe wall system. Moreover the calculation methods for key optical and thermal parameters of the transparent element, including U-value, solar transmittance, and solar reduction factor are presented.

The evaluation of dynamic solar façade systems, such as the Solar Air Heating Façade (SAHF), relies on specific KPIs. These metrics are essential for assessing the façade's ability to regulate heat transfer, optimize solar gains, and enhance energy efficiency throughout varying environmental conditions.

The solar efficiency indicator, denoted as η_{sol} [8], is usually employed to quantify the ratio between the thermal energy delivered to the indoor space by the preheated airflow Q_{supply} and the total solar radiation incident on the wall's vertical surface Q_{sol} .

In the case of Indoor Air Curtain IAC mode:

$$\eta_{sol} = \frac{\sum_n^m Q_{sup\ ply}}{\sum_n^m Q_{sol}} \cdot 100 = \frac{\sum_n^m \dot{V} \cdot C_p \cdot \rho \cdot (T_{a-up} - T_{in})}{\sum_n^m S_{ol-i-AV} \cdot A} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

In the case Supply Air Façade (SAF):

$$\eta_{sol} = \frac{\sum_n^m Q_{sup\ ply}}{\sum_n^m Q_{sol}} \cdot 100 = \frac{\sum_n^m \dot{V} \cdot C_p \cdot \rho \cdot (T_{a-up} - T_{a-ext})}{\sum_n^m S_{ol-i-AV} \cdot A} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

Where n and m refer to the referenced period, \dot{V} is the airflow rate in [m³/s], C_p is the air specific heat in [J/kg·K], ρ is the air density in [kg/m³], $S_{ol-i-AV}$ [Wh] is the solar irradiation, T_{a-ext} is the outdoor temperature in [°C], and A is the surface area of each facade. T_{a-up} is used for calculations instead of T_{a-out} , as the goal of the study is the evaluation of the component's efficiency, and hence the heat losses attributed to the air distribution inside the indoor environment were neglected. Nevertheless, this quantity does not consider the full TW performance, as it completely neglects the thermal behavior of the massive storage wall.

To incorporate this aspect, a second performance indicator, the total efficiency η_{tot} [9], was introduced. This metric also accounts for the heat exchange occurring between the massive storage wall and the indoor air Q_{cond} .

$$\eta_{tot} = \frac{\sum_n^m Q_{sup\ ply} + \sum_n^m Q_{cond}}{\sum_n^m Q_{sol}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{\sum_n^m [\dot{V} \cdot C_p \cdot \rho \cdot (T_{a-up} - T_{a-ext})] + \sum_n^m [h_{si} \cdot (T_{st} - T_{in}) \cdot A]}{\sum_n^m S_{ol-i-AV} \cdot A} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

Finally, an additional metric is useful, the thermal buffering efficiency η_{buf} to evaluate the performance of the SAHF when used in the thermal buffer mode. This index was determined considering only the time intervals when the ventilation system was deactivated.

$$\eta_{buf} = 1 - \frac{\sum_n^m (T_{in} - T_{cav})}{\sum_n^m (T_{in} - T_{ext})} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

Where T_{cav} represents the average temperature of the air cavity at each time-step.

To evaluate the performance of lamella integration in terms of both thermal insulation and solar control, the analysis was guided by three KPIs, carefully selected to quantify the system's thermal and optical behavior:

- thermal transmittance ($U - value$), which reflects the insulating capability;
- solar transmittance (τ), indicating the solar radiation passing through the components;
- solar reduction factor (RF), which measures the system's ability to reduce solar gains.

Being these metrics well known a short description is here provided

The U-value represents the rate of heat transfer through the transparent element and was calculated in accordance with the EN ISO 6946:2017 [10], following the simplified formula:

$$U = \frac{1}{R_{si} + R_1 + R_2 + \dots + R_n + R_{se}} \quad (6)$$

Where R_{si} is the internal surface thermal resistance, R_{se} is the external surface thermal resistance and R_1 , R_2 and R_n are the thermal resistances of each layer.

The solar transmittance (τ), calculated using Equation (7), represents the percentage of solar radiation transmitted through the sample in relation to the incident global solar irradiance I . It quantifies the system's ability to allow solar energy to pass through:

$$\tau = \left(\frac{I_{sample}}{I_{baseline}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

Where I_{sample} is the solar irradiance measured with the tested sample in place and $I_{baseline}$ is the solar irradiance measured without the sample (reference condition).

The solar reduction factor (RF), described by Equation (8), measures the percentage by which a component reduces incoming solar radiation compared to the baseline configuration. It is expressed as:

$$RF = 1 - \left(\frac{\tau_{analyzed\ component}}{\tau_{baseline}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

Where $\tau_{analyzed\ component}$ is the solar transmittance of the component under study and $\tau_{baseline}$ is the solar transmittance of the baseline component (PC16).

C) Prototype description and experimental assessment

This section describes the experimental evaluation of the SAHF concept integrating aerogel-filled polycarbonate and wooden lamella. Experiments were conducted in two setups: the BET-cell (double climatic chamber) and the DHFM (dynamic heat flow meter) to assess thermal and optical performance. Moreover, the full-scale prototypes installed in a real building are described.

The energy performance of the developed SAHF system has been investigated in labs and under actual operating conditions, through a full-scale experimental campaign conducted on a residential building located near Turin, Italy, as shown in figure 1. SAHF was subjected to continuous monitoring throughout two entire winter seasons, providing valuable insight into its real-world performance and contribution to space heating. This long-term monitoring approach addresses a key shortcoming found in existing literature, where experimental studies are often limited to short observation periods spanning only a few days or weeks. The findings from this research contribute to a deeper understanding of the thermal dynamics and effectiveness of fan-assisted SAHF systems when integrated into existing buildings under actual operating conditions.

Figure 1. Construction phase of the full scale experimental prototypes and integration in a real building (three different solutions installed in order to allow comparisons under different condition).

The laboratory performance assessment

A dedicated experimental approach was employed to assess the thermal transmittance (U-value) and solar transmission properties of the transparent elements used on the developed SAHF system. Thermal performance testing was conducted using a Heat Flux Meter (HFM) apparatus (figure2-a).

Moreover, in order to identify the best balance between energy efficiency and architectural integration a lamella covering systems was designed and investigated in a double climatic chamber equipped with an artificial sun (BET-CELL) (figure2-b).

The tested lamella setups were specifically designed to be integrated into the full-scale system described in the previous section. Each configuration featured lightweight, horizontal lamella elements, designed to enhance thermal performance while preserving structural integrity.

Figure 2. (a) Heat Flux Meter (HFM) setup, (b) Climatic chamber (BET-CELL) equipped with an artificial sun.

Methodology

For the thermal transmittance study, various alveolar polycarbonate samples (figure3), characterized by different numbers of internal cavities and void fractions, were experimentally tested in two conditions: unfilled (containing air) and filled with aerogel. The equivalent thermal conductivity for both air-filled configurations and Silica-Aerogel-filled was measured using a LaserComp Fox 600 Heat Flux Meter, in accordance with the ASTM C518 standard [11]. For the aerogel infill, a granular aerogel material supplied by CABOT, featuring a thermal conductivity of 0.0122 W/m.K, was utilized. Four different polycarbonate panels were initially tested and later used to build a small-scale prototype. For laboratory testing, each sample needed to have a measurable area of 25.4 cm². Although the front surface of the panels measured 40 cm², their thicknesses varied: two panels were 1 cm thick, one was 1.6 cm, and the final one was 2 cm thick.

Figure 3. Polycarbonate panels.

For solar transmission performance, different configurations combining polycarbonate panels, silica-Aerogel insulation, and lamella systems with varying coatings and geometries were evaluated. The prototype setup, which included a lamella box and a polycarbonate layer, was consistently positioned in front of the artificial light source to ensure uniform exposure during testing as illustrated in figure 4. The prototype consists of a precisely constructed lamella box, as shown in figure 5 It features a wooden frame where uniform horizontal lamella is integrated. The lamella box has dimensions of 40 × 40 cm, with a polycarbonate layer positioned behind the lamella. The lamella was

coated with three different materials: wood, white paint, and aluminum. Additionally, the effect of the inclination was investigated, as shown in figure 6, including a vertical baseline at 0°, and inclined positions at 20° and 45° to explore the influence of lamella inclination on solar transmission and thermal performance. A fixed distance of one meter between the light source and the prototype was maintained throughout the experiments. The lighting system consisted of four high-intensity projectors designed to illuminate a surface area of 1040 × 1140 cm², delivering an approximate irradiance of 1000 W/m² a value representative of clear sky conditions during peak solar hours. Solar radiation measurements were carried out using two Hukseflux LP02 second-class pyranometers, installed behind the polycarbonate panel to capture localized variations in transmitted irradiance. For each tested configuration, the transmitted solar intensity was continuously recorded at 10-second intervals over a total test period of approximately 15 minutes. Only the data from the final 5 minutes, corresponding to the stabilized phase, were used in the analysis.

Figure 4. Lamella prototype under artificial sun in the BET-cell.

Figure 5. Different configurations of the tested lamella samples.

Figure 6. Experimental arrangement of the sample positioned at tilt angles of 0°, 20°, and 45°.

Results and discussions

The integration of Silica-Aerogel as an infill material led to a significant reduction in thermal transmittance of approximately 40%. As shown in Figure 7, the reported values are compared to a reference (Ref. value) provided by the manufacturer [11]. Due to the limited cavity size, it was not feasible to fill the 10 mm-thick polycarbonate panel (with four internal chambers) with aerogel; thus, this panel was tested in its empty state. The lowest U-value recorded was 1.19 W/m²·K for the 20 mm-thick polycarbonate panel filled with Silica-Aerogel, representing a 41.8% reduction compared to its counterpart with air-filled cavities.

Figure 7. U-Value of all alveolar polycarbonate panels, tested with both air cavities and aerogel infill.

The bar chart of figure 8 displays the solar transmission (τ) for various SAHF configurations. Among all tested setups, PC10 exhibits the highest solar transmittance, exceeding 70%, while PC16 + B2 45° and PC16 + Aerogel 45° show some of the lowest values, indicating the impact of lamella orientation and Silica-Aerogel insulation on solar penetration.

Figure 8. Solar transmission (τ) for various SAHF configurations.

Figure 9 (left) highlights how different lamella types based on material and width affect the optical performance of the SAHF system by analyzing the (RF), which quantifies how much solar radiation is stopped compared to a standalone polycarbonate layer (PC16). Lower RF values indicate higher solar transmission while higher RF values signify stronger shading and insulation performance. Among all configurations, aluminum-coated lamellas (B2 and A2) demonstrated the lowest RF values, with B2 (2 cm width) achieving 19.9% RF and a solar transmission ratio of 42.8%. A2 (3 cm width) followed with an RF of 30.4% and a transmission ratio of 37.2%. These results underline the superior balance aluminum coatings offer between allowing sunlight in and minimizing heat loss, particularly when using narrower lamella widths. White-coated lamellae (B1 and A1) showed intermediate performance, with RF values between 38% and 39%, and solar transmission ratios around 32–33%. These provide moderate solar reflection and shading, which could suit climates requiring more controlled solar gain. Wooden lamellas (B and A) presented the highest RF values (up to 43.35% for B), indicating a strong shading effect and lower solar transmission. While these configurations reduce incoming solar radiation significantly, they enhance thermal insulation due to wood's natural properties, favoring applications prioritizing comfort and reduced heat gains over daylighting. In summary, aluminum-coated B2 stands out as the most efficient solution for maximizing solar transmission and energy gain, whereas wooden and white-coated lamellas offer greater shading and thermal protection. The choice of lamella type should therefore align with the specific energy, comfort, and daylighting goals of the building application.

The right side of Figure 9 illustrates the thermal behavior of PC10 and PC16 polycarbonate configurations, both with and without Silica-Aerogel infill. The PC16 system without aerogel shows a solar transmission ratio of 53.4%, indicating a relatively high level of heat transfer through the facade. This suggests that the PC16 alone is not particularly effective in limiting conductive or convective heat transfer.

In comparison, PC10 without aerogel achieves a higher solar transmission ratio of 71.6%. Although its multi-cavity structure enhances thermal resistance, it may also increase convective and radiative heat exchange within the cavities, leading to greater solar gain. This underlines the benefit of incorporating materials like Silica-Aerogel to mitigate such effects. The addition of Silica-Aerogel markedly improves the thermal performance of both

configurations by reducing solar transmission and enhancing insulation. For PC16, the aerogel lowers the transmission ratio to 43.4%, corresponding to a Reduction Factor (RF) of 18.7%. In the case of PC10, the aerogel reduces the transmission to 62.5%, with a corresponding RF of 12.8%. These findings confirm Silica-Aerogel's effectiveness in limiting heat conduction due to its inherently low thermal conductivity.

Figure 9. Comparison of Solar Transmission and Reduction Factor for Different Lamella Types (Left); PC10 and PC16 Configurations with and without Silica Aerogel (Right).

Figure 10 presents the solar transmission ratios and reduction factors (RF) for three PC16 panel configurations: the unmodified panel, the panel filled with Silica-Aerogel, and the panel combined with aluminum-coated lamella B2. These parameters were evaluated under three solar incidence angles (0°, 20°, and 45°) to assess both optical and thermal performance. At 0°, the highest solar transmission (53.4%) was recorded for the unmodified PC16, while the addition of aerogel and lamella B2 reduced transmission to around 43% and 42.8%, respectively, with corresponding RF values near 18–20%. As the angle increased to 20°, transmission values declined across all cases, with PC16 + Aerogel and PC16 + B2 reaching RF values of nearly 30% and 32%, respectively. At 45°, transmission dropped significantly, especially for PC16 + B2, which achieved the lowest transmission (21.2%) and the highest RF (60.2%). Overall, the basic PC16 allowed more solar gain but offered limited insulation. In contrast, the use of aerogel and aluminum-coated lamella notably enhanced thermal resistance, particularly at higher angles of solar incidence. These results highlight the effectiveness of combining low-conductivity and reflective materials for optimizing the performance of solar air heating facades, depending on orientation and climate needs.

Figure 10. Impact of angle variations.

In-situ monitoring activity on different SAHF configurations

To assess the impact of architectural integration on the thermal and solar performance of SAHF systems, the monitoring activity was divided into two main phases. The first phase, conducted during the 2023–2024 heating season, served as the reference scenario and focused on baseline measurements without advanced integration strategies. In the second phase, 2024–2025, the SAHF modules were enhanced through architectural integration, including the application of optimized lamella configurations and the use of advanced insulating materials, the Silica-Aerogel.

Methodology

Three full-scale SAHF walls were integrated into the building as shown in figure 11. The SAHF modules were installed on the South-facing façade, specifically on the second floor, occupying the uninsulated wall sections located between the glazed elements and positioned below the roof overhang. To enhance solar absorption, the external surface of the storage walls was coated with matte black paint. Unlike conventional systems that often employ single or double glazing, ventilated cavities were created using hollow polycarbonate panels, which offer a balance of low weight, satisfactory thermal transmittance in line with European standards [12], and higher solar transmittance compared to traditional glazing systems. The evaluation of the three modules was conducted over a representative week from December 14th to December 19th, 2023, during which the heating system was turned off. The selected period included six consecutive fully sunny days, characterized by high incident solar irradiation (Sol_i_AV) and relatively low outdoor temperatures, ranging between 0.5°C and nearly 15°C.

Figure 11. Experimental setup of SAHF without lamella.

Figure 12. Schematic representation of the three experimental modules.

Following a series of experimental tests on lamella prototypes with various surface coatings and configurations both with and without silica aerogel the B2 configuration, featuring an aluminum-coated surface, was selected for its optimal balance between thermal performance and solar transmission. This configuration was integrated into the full-scale SAHF system in December 2024 and was then monitored until the spring of 2025. The aluminum-coated lamella was installed in Wall B. Meanwhile, Walls A and C were equipped with wooden lamellaas illustrated in figure 13.

Figure 13. Experimental setup of SAHF coupled with lamella.

Results and discussions

This section presents all the results developed during the 2023-2024 period, including detailed analyses and findings related to the performance of the Trombe wall system.

Figure 14 illustrates the daily variation of external air temperature (T_{a_ext} , blue line), horizontal solar irradiance (Sol_h_AV , grey line), and incoming solar irradiance (Sol_i_AV , orange line) during the experimental period.

Figure14. Variation of boundary conditions.

Since Walls A and C follow the same principle, their experimental results are presented together. Figures 15 and 16 show the temperature profiles of the air in the cavities of Wall A and Wall C, respectively, with thermocouple data from different cavity positions and the inlet/outlet of the exhaust pipe. The indoor room temperature is also shown in red.

Figure 15: Temperature profile in the ventilated cavity, indoor, and outdoor environments for Wall A

Figure 16: T Temperature profile in the cavity, indoor, and outdoor environments for Wall C.

Figure 17 shows the variation of surface temperature variables along with the outdoor temperature for Wall A, and Figure 18 presents the same for Wall C. It is evident that the massive walls reach high temperatures, with Wall A exceeding 60°C on the sunniest days, about 50°C higher than the outdoor temperature. The slightly higher Ts_2 values of Wall A are due to elevated temperatures in the kitchen. Notably, the wall temperature remains close to 20°C even at night, and the polycarbonate maintains an internal surface temperature (Ts_1) over 10°C higher than the outdoor temperature. The indoor surface temperature also shows an increasing trend, which, although seemingly modest, is significant given the wall's high thermal inertia.

Figure 17. Surface and outdoor temperature profiles of Wall A.

Figure 18. Surface and outdoor temperature profiles of Wall C.

Figure 19 presents the air temperature variables in the cavity and the indoor environment. Wall B operates in TB mode until December 17th, after which it transitions to SAF mode. The indoor temperature (T_{in}) remains stable between 18°C and 19°C throughout the week, indicating consistent indoor conditions. It is important to note that the room behind Wall B and C (the dining room) was seldom occupied by the residents during the monitored period.

Figure 19. Temperature profile of the ventilated cavity, the indoor and outdoor environment for Wall B.

During the first three days, Wall B operates in TB mode with no ventilation. As shown in figure 20 the middle cavity temperature (Ta_{mid}) peaks at 63.1°C , followed by Ta_{down} and Ta_{up} , which remains 8°C cooler due to roof shading. At night, the temperature follows a buoyancy-driven profile. On the next three days, when Wall B operates as a SAF, the fan-driven airflow causes the lower part of the façade to have the lowest temperature, with the middle part reaching up to 60°C , $3.5\text{--}4^{\circ}\text{C}$ warmer than the upper part. The air entering the room is $4^{\circ}\text{C}\text{--}5^{\circ}\text{C}$ cooler than the upper façade temperature, and at night, the temperature profile returns to a buoyancy-dominated state.

Figure 20. Surface and outdoor temperature profiles of Wall B.

Despite identical configurations, Wall A and Wall C exhibit significant thermal behavior differences presented in figure 21. On December 19th, during active ventilation, Wall C generally shows higher temperatures for most variables. For instance, Ta_{down} reaches 41°C at 13:45 for Wall A, while Wall C peaks at 38.4°C at 15:00. These differences are due to shading effects and indoor temperature variations, with Wall A receiving no early morning shading and having slightly higher indoor air temperature. At 14:00, both walls show a temperature drop due to column shading, which is more pronounced for Wall A. Ta_{mid} shows the most significant difference, with Wall C reaching 56.3°C , about 7°C higher than Wall A, due to shading effects from lateral partitions and a larger column. Ta_{up} is similar for both walls, with Wall C slightly higher (44.4°C) than Wall A (42.7°C). Despite Wall C's higher temperatures, Wall A's outlet air is warmer due to lower heat losses from the wall, with Ta_{out_A} reaching 38.4°C at 14:45, while Ta_{out_C} peaks at 37.4°C at 15:00.

Figure 21. Profile of the air temperature variation in the cavities of Wall A and Wall C on December 19th during the fan operation hours.

The comparison between Wall B and Wall C reveals that Wall B performs better (figure 22), mainly due to its larger size and reduced shading from lateral obstructions. On December 19th, during mechanical ventilation, Wall B's Ta_{out} is 12°C higher than Wall C's (49.3°C vs. 37.4°C), and Ta_{mid} is 2.4°C higher. Tsi values are similar, with Wall B slightly higher but not exceeding a 1°C difference. Wall B's superior performance is attributed to its larger area and more optimal positioning.

Figure 22. Comparison of key temperature variables profile for Wall B and Wall C.

The actual efficiency in figure 23 considers the sunlight area for each wall at each time-step, while the effect of diffusing radiation on shaded areas was found to be negligible (0% to 0.8%). The results are based on the representative week, but the highest daily performance occurred on December 25th, a day with high solar irradiance and outdoor temperatures exceeding 15°C. On this day, Wall B demonstrated the highest heating capacity, with an actual efficiency of 23.2%, followed by Wall C, which outperformed Wall A by approximately 1%.

The potential efficiency (η_{sol}), which accounts for the total incident solar radiation, was significantly higher, particularly for Wall B, which exceeded 30%. Although Wall C had a slightly higher actual efficiency than Wall A, Wall A exhibited greater potential efficiency. This suggests that Wall A, despite its shading, has a higher potential to heat indoor air effectively, likely due to the warmer adjacent kitchen room that reduces heat loss from the solid masonry.

Figure 23. Daily actual and potential efficiency η_{sol} for the three façade configurations on December 25th.

D) Development and calibration of a CFD numerical model

This section outlines the creation of a CFD model to simulate the thermal behavior of the SAHF system. The model is developed to replicate experimental setup, incorporating material properties, boundary conditions, and ventilation effects. Calibration is performed using experimental data to ensure the model accurately predicts temperature distribution and airflow dynamics within the façade.

To better understand and predict the thermal behavior of the (SAHF), a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model was developed using ANSYS FLUENT. The numerical model accurately reproduced the geometry and boundary conditions of the full-scale experimental setup, specifically focusing on the supply wall configuration (wall B) (figure24). The model included the polycarbonate glazing, the air cavity, and the storage wall, along with relevant features such as the fan, inlet and outlet openings, and internal heat sources. Temperature sensors positioned at

different heights within the air cavity (T_{a_down} , T_{a_mid} , T_{a_up}), as well as surface temperatures (T_{s_ext} , T_{s1} , T_{s2}) and outlet air temperature (T_{Outlet}), were used for model calibration and validation.

Figure 24. Full-scale experimental setup of wall B and schematic measurement points and airflow paths.

The CFD model

A structured mesh was generated, comprising 3,180,271 cells illustrated in figure 25, to accurately resolve the convective airflow within the cavity. The boundary conditions were defined based on measured values obtained from the experimental campaign, with special attention given to the solar radiation input, outdoor air temperature, and wall surface properties. The numerical analysis was conducted under steady-state conditions to match the stable environmental scenario recorded on December 19th, 2024, at 13:00. The model employed the SIMPLE algorithm for pressure-velocity coupling and the k-omega SST turbulence model for resolving turbulent flow structures within the ventilated air cavity and DO model for the solar radiation model.

Figure 25. Modeling and Meshing.

Model validation

The CFD model was evaluated by comparing simulated temperature profiles against experimental measurements collected during the same time frame. Key points of comparison included the outlet air temperature (T_{Outlet}), air temperatures at various vertical positions inside the air cavity ($T_{\text{a_UP}}$, $T_{\text{a_Mid}}$, $T_{\text{a_Down}}$), the external surface temperature ($T_{\text{s_ext}}$), the storage wall surface temperatures (T_{s1} , T_{s2}), and the indoor air and surface temperatures (T_{si} , T_{ind}).

As shown in Figure 26, the numerical and experimental results exhibited a strong correlation with a relative error approximatively of 13%. The largest discrepancies were noted at $T_{\text{a_Down}}$ and $T_{\text{s_ext}}$, which can be attributed to factors such as measurement uncertainties, idealized radiation modeling, and simplifications in boundary condition definitions. Moreover, the wall was partially shaded in the real case, and this was neglected in the simulation,

The outlet temperature (T_{Outlet}) recorded experimentally reached approximately 48°C, while the simulation predicted slightly higher values, around 52°C. Similarly, the storage wall surface temperatures (T_{s1} and T_{s2}) were well captured by the model, confirming its capability to reproduce the heat storage and release behaviour of the massive wall. The indoor-side temperature (T_{si}) and the indoor air temperature (T_{ind}) also exhibited close alignment, validating the model's accuracy in estimating the system's contribution to indoor thermal comfort.

Figure26. Comparison between Experimental and CFD results.

Figure27. Temperature and velocity CFD contours.

The CFD results in figure 27 illustrate the airflow behavior within wall B. On the left, the temperature contour shows a clear gradient ranging from 18°C to approximately 63°C. The highest temperatures are concentrated along the absorbing wall, indicating strong solar energy absorption. As air moves upward along this heated surface, its temperature gradually decreases, suggesting effective heat transfer into the cavity. The cooler zones in the rest of the cavity reflect natural thermal stratification, typical of buoyancy-driven flow. On the right, the velocity magnitude contour reveals airflow dynamics, with values ranging from 0 to 2.2 m/s. The highest velocities are observed near the top outlet, where heated air exits the system.

Conclusions

A novel concept of SAHF integrating lamella systems and silica-aerogel-enhanced polycarbonate panels has been developed, aiming to enhance its thermal performance while maintaining architectural appeal. Through a combination of experimental testing (BET-CELL), real-scale monitoring, and validated CFD simulations, the research moreover established a comprehensive performance assessment framework useful to customize the solution under different boundary conditions, providing valuable guidance for architects and engineers in developing energy-efficient façade systems tailored to both climatic conditions and architectural requirements. Findings demonstrates that lamella and Silica-Aerogel integration within SAHF systems can significantly enhance energy performance, highlighting the importance of design choices such as lamella material, coating, and panel composition on the overall system efficiency.

Analyses at building scale currently on-going demonstrate the high potential of the developed system in achieving current target on energy efficiency in the building sector.

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